

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF STUDY HABITS OF BOYS AND GIRLS OF INTERMEDIATE LEVEL

Ms. Sunanda Singh

B. Ed (Isabella Thoburn Degree College, Lucknow)

M.A. (English Literature) (Isabella Thoburn Degree College, Lucknow), M.Ed

Abstract:- The present research is conducted by the researcher in order to study the difference between the study habits of intermediate level students based on their gender. In present scenario of tough competition and increasing demand of knowledge, study habits plays a very important role in a student's life to achieve his goals. Education is the most effective instrument of social and economic change and it is the education that determines the level of prosperity, welfare, and security of the people. Education has always been concerned with the prediction of scholastic achievement or academic achievement of individuals. Generally, academic achievement refers to the extent or degree of mastery in certain areas of studies. Hence, it has to be relevant and it would be reflected through the academic achievement of the students. Academic achievement means knowledge attained or skill developed in the school subjects, usually designated by the test scores or by marks assigned by teachers or by both. In the sense, the achievement of pupils in the so-called academic subjects such as languages, arithmetic, general science etc. Academic achievement is the important outcome of any educational setup. The task of learning is not one sided. Efficient learning depends not only on good teaching alone, but on satisfactory learning procedures also. Efficient learning depends upon the learner's ability to schedule his/her time, plans of study, and habit of concentration, note taking, mental review and the judicious application of learning and so on. In other words, learning involves the development of proper study habits and skills. The term study habit means various methods and practices adapted by the students in their studies. Poor study habit is one of the biggest and most persistent problem among the students. Effective study consists of much more than mere memorizing fact. It calls for knowing where and how to obtain facts and the ability to make best use of time. It means that the student must be able to organize, classify, and arrange facts in their proper relationship to the subject being studied. Study habits includes student's habit of concentration, notes taking, time budgeting and study method. Students as well as parents now a day are running pillar to post to get the readymade notes to get through exams and neglect the important sources of knowledge. The main cause of this is that our present system of education has failed to inculcate good study habits. It is the cry of time to give stress on study habits because these help in learning. 'Study habits' is like a 'supper source' of acquiring information in comparison to other learning aids. The individual learner gradually develops certain study habits to comprehend the concepts of subjects. The present day students are haphazard in their study habits as they select the way of least resistance and resort to cheap notes to get through the examination neglecting other means and media of acquiring knowledge. Due to lack of proper study habits, qualitative achievement of student is not witnessed many times. Study habits play a decisive role in the academic life of a person. It covers broadly individual's mode of regularizing study behaviour and sensitization to curricular and extracurricular books, interest in newspapers and magazines on one hand and some personal habits like reading aloud or silently in group or in isolation etc. on the other. Poor habits of study not only retard school progress but develop frustration, destroy initiative and confidence and make prominent the feeling of worthlessness towards himself and the subject of study whereas effective methods ensure success, happiness, and sense of accomplishment. Learning has been deeply rooted in Indian traditions. Reading, which is a long-term habit starting with the very early ages, is prominent gateway to the knowledge room. It can be assumed as a practice that assists individuals to gain creativeness and develops their critical thinking capacities. In this sense, study habit is an important tool for the development of personalities and mental capacities of individuals. In addition to personal and mental developments, study is an access to social, economic, and civic life. Moreover, all study patterns in terms of emotional response enhance emotional satisfaction of individuals. For continuous and regular progress in education process, learners need to enhance their study habits so as to fulfill individual improvement. Teachers teach all students collectively but not all students get the same grades. At this stage, we see underachievers and high achievers in educational achievements. There may be number of reasons but one of the reason may be the students fail to make good habits to learn the lessons. Study habits of

the children could play important role in learning process reflected in the academic achievement of student's. There exists a positive and significant relationship between study habits and academic achievement.

Study habits and its correlates is a popular field of research. Many studies conducted on the study habits of the students in relation to their academic achievement, intelligence, self-concept, self-esteem, emotional maturity, adjustment, coping styles, time perception etc. Very little research is conducted on the study habits of intermediate students in relation to their gender differences. In the light of the observations, personal experience and the literature available encouraged the researcher to undertake a study to find out whether there are any differences in the study habits of students of Intermediate level in relation to their gender.

In today's world of tough competition, it is the need of the hour that students should develop proper study habits. They should know the proper, efficient, and systematic way of learning to face various competitions. If the parents are well aware of the situation, they can guide their children or make arrangements for the same. Hence, the Researcher felt the need to find out, whether there is any difference between study habits of boys and girls, so that they can be guided in proper way to develop good study habits accordingly.

Keeping this aspect in view the researcher decided to conduct the present research on the topic "A

Comparative Study of Study Habits of Boys and Girls of Intermediate Level."

To conduct the present study four objectives were formulated: 1.) to compare the study habits of boys and girls of government Schools in Lucknow City. 2.) To compare the study habits of boys and girls of private schools in Lucknow city. 3.) To compare the study habits of boys and girls of science & Arts group students of government & private schools of Lucknow city. 4.) To compare the study habits of boys and girls of private and government schools of Lucknow city. Following Null hypotheses is formulated to find out the difference the difference between the study habits of boys and girls of intermediate level of Lucknow city - 1.) There is no significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of government schools .2.) There is no significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of private schools . 3.) There is no significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of science and arts group students of government and private schools. 4.) There is no significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of government and private schools.

The present study is a descriptive survey research. The students of Intermediate level of government and private schools of Lucknow District constitute the population of study. A representative sample of 200 students of class XI has been taken as a sample of the study. 100 girls of private and government schools and 100 boys of private and government schools are selected respectively. Simple random sampling method is used to select the sample for the research.

The results shows that girls belonging to government and private both the schools have better study habits than that of boys .Students belonging to Science stream have better study habits than arts stream. The result also shows that students of private schools have better study habits in comparison of government schools. Hence, it can be concluded that girls have performed much better than boys and have better study habits than boys. Academic achievement of the students is associated with their study habits. Hence, proper study habits should be developed among the students for attaining good Academic achievement.

Keyword: Study Habits, Intermediate Level

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is the most effective instrument of social and economic change and it is the education that determines the level of prosperity, welfare and security of the people. Education has always been concerned with the prediction of scholastic achievement or academic achievement of individuals. Generally academic achievement refers to the extent or degree of mastery in certain areas of studies. Hence, it has to be relevant and it would be reflected through the academic achievement of the students. Academic achievement means knowledge attained or skill developed in the school subjects, usually designated by the test scores or by marks assigned by teachers or by both. In the sense the achievement of pupils in the so called academic subjects such as languages, arithmetic, general science etc. Academic achievement is the important outcome of any educational setup.

Education is universally recognized as one of the most fundamental building blocks for a country's progress as it develops the inner abilities and power of an individual. It involves the cultivation of an innocent mind, by instilling values and principles. It also includes the development of skills along with the achievement of one's

physical, mental and social development. To put it in technical terms, education consists of defined phases starting from formal education i.e. primary, secondary, higher education and ideally it never ends. If simply stated, it means the process of gaining knowledge, inculcating forms of proper conduct and acquiring technical competency. The process of education is believed to begin in the womb that continues through all the phases of our life as knowledge is oceanic and one can never claim to have acquired all of it.

The task of learning is not one sided. Efficient learning depends not only on good teaching alone, but on satisfactory learning procedures also. Efficient learning depends upon the learner's ability to schedule his/her time, plans of study, and habit of concentration, note taking, mental review and the judicious application of learning and so on. In other words, learning involves the development of proper study habits and skills.

The term study habit means various methods and practices adapted by the students in their studies. Poor study habit is one of the biggest and most persistent problem among the students. Effective study consists of much more than mere memorizing fact. It calls for knowing where and how to obtain facts and the ability to make best use of time. It means that the student must be able to organize, classify and arrange facts in their proper relationship to the subject being studied. Study habits includes student's habit of concentration, notes taking, time budgeting and study method .

The word 'study habits' comprises of two words i.e. study + habits. 'Study' means application of mind to the requirements of knowledge, study akin to be eager, the diligent and a state of absorbed contemplation. 'Habit' refers to a sense of behavior that has become more or less fixed. Habits signify a way of acting or thinking frequently enough leading to unconscious behavior. Thus study habits refer to acquisition of knowledge and skills through more or less permanent modes of studying. According to Tussing (1962) "Study habits are autonomously learned behavior patterns that enable the students to acquire how to study." According to Good's Dictionary of Education (1973), "Study habit is the tendency of a pupil or student to study when the opportunities are given, the pupil's way of studying whether systematic or unsystematic, efficient or inefficient etc".

Students as well as parents now a day are running pillar to post to get the readymade notes to get through exams and neglect the important sources of knowledge. The main cause of this is that our present system of education has failed to inculcate good study habits. It is the cry of time to give stress on study habits because these help in learning. 'Study habits' is like a 'supper source' of acquiring information in comparison to other learning aids. The individual learner gradually develops certain study habits to comprehend the concepts of subjects. The present day students are haphazard in their study habits as they select the way of least resistance and resort to cheap notes to get through the examination neglecting other means and media of acquiring knowledge. Due to lack of proper study habits, qualitative achievement of student is not witnessed many times. Study habits play a decisive role in the academic life of a person. It covers broadly individual's mode of regularizing study behaviour and sensitization to curricular and extracurricular books, interest in newspapers and magazines on one hand and some personal habits like reading aloud or silently in group or in isolation etc. on the other. Poor habits of study not only retard school progress but develop frustration, destroy initiative and confidence and make prominent the feeling of worthlessness towards himself and the subject of study whereas effective methods ensure success, happiness and sense of accomplishment.

There is need for concentration on study habit because it helps the new type of learning. In spite of the growing role of learning aids, study habit will continue to be the most important method of acquiring information. Developing good study habit and skill is an asset. Kulshresta (1992) suggested "a definite purpose and place for study. He further suggested seeking physical conditions that are favorable for mental activity, followed by a definite time schedule for study". Thus study habits imply a sort of more or less permanent mode or method of studying. Individuals have their own way of studying. It has also been found that those who have good study habits excel others having equal intelligence in academic achievement.

Efficient learning depends upon the development of efficient study habits and skills and as such one of the continuous objectives of teaching should be the improvement of study habits and skills of the students. From the practical point of view, it has been very often seen that teachers come across such students who appear to have above average scholastic aptitudes, yet they are doing very poorly in their courses of study. A large majority of these seem to have faulty study habits. Proper guidance to the students would change their faulty study habits into desirable ones, as such study habits are important for higher academic achievement of students and it is also important for them to make use of their leisure time. The later aspect is also important for adults who are now in job, particularly for the teachers. Thus study habits, which is genetic than specific in terms of its importance.

NEED AND SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Learning has been deeply rooted in Indian traditions. Reading, which is a long-term habit starting with the very early ages, is prominent gateway to the knowledge room. It can be assumed as a practice that assists individuals to gain creativeness and develops their critical thinking capacities. In this sense, study habit is an important tool for the development of personalities and mental capacities of individuals. In addition to personal and mental developments, study is an access to social, economic and civic life (Clark and Rumbold, 2006). Moreover, all study patterns in terms of emotional response enhance emotional satisfaction of individuals (Sarland, 1991). For continuous and regular progress in education process, learners need to be enhanced to gain study habits so as to fulfill individual improvement. Teachers teach all students collectively but all students do not get the same grades. At this stage we see underachievers and high achievers in educational achievements. There may be number of reasons but one of the reason may be the students fail to make good habits to learn the lessons. Study habits of the children could play important role in learning process reflected in the academic achievement of student's. There exists a positive and significant relationship between study habits and academic achievement.

Study habits and its correlates is a popular field of research. Many studies were conducted on the study habits of the students in relation to their academic achievement, intelligence, self-concept, self-esteem, emotional maturity, adjustment, coping styles, time perception etc. Very little research is conducted on the study habits of intermediate students in relation to their gender differences. In the light of the observations, personal experience and also on the literature available the researcher is prompted to undertake a study to find out whether there are any differences in the study habits students of Intermediate level in relation to their gender differences.

In today's world of tough competition, it is the need of the hour that students should develop proper study habits. They should know the proper, efficient and systematic way of learning to face various competitions. If the parents are well aware of the situation they can guide their children or make arrangements for the same. Hence, the Researcher felt the need to find out, whether there is any difference between study habits of boys and girls, so that they can be guided in proper way to develop good study habits accordingly.

1.6 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem of the study can be stated as follows:-

“A Comparative Study of Study Habits of Boys and Girls of Intermediate Level”

1.7 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:-

- To compare the study habits of boys and girls of government Schools in Lucknow City.
- To compare the study habits of boys and girls of private schools in Lucknow city.
- To compare the study habits of boys and girls of science & Arts group students of government & private schools of Lucknow city.
- To compare the study habits of boys and girls of private and government schools.

1.8 HYPOTHESES OF THE STUDY:-

- There is no significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of government schools.
- There is no significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of private schools.
- There is no significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of science and arts group students of government and private schools.
- There is no significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of government and private schools.

OPERATIONAL DEFINITION OF THE KEY TERMS:-

1. STUDY:-

Study is the activity of learning or gaining knowledge, either from books or by examining things in the world. It is also the act of considering or examining materials in detail.

2. HABITS:-

Habits refer to a thing that someone does often and almost without thinking; especially something that is hard to stop doing. It is usual behavior.

3. STUDY HABITS:-

Study habits have been considered to be constituted of different kinds of study behavior. Such as budgeting time, reading ability, note taking, preparation for examination.

4. INTERMEDIATE LEVEL STUDENTS:-

Intermediate level refers to Secondary (IX and X) and Senior Secondary (XI and XII) classes.

5. GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS:-

Where Sole management of government officials.

6. PRIVATE SCHOOLS:-

Managed by private organizations or individuals, either partially or totally.

1.10 DELIMITATION OF THE STUDY:-

- This study is limited to Lucknow District only.
- Students of class XI only taken as sample.
- The study will be confined to only urban areas of Lucknow District.
- This study consists of 200 Students of class XI only taken as sample.
- The study is confined to three schools only.
- The age of the students ranges from 16-18 years.
- Limitations of the tool and technique used in the study will also be the limitation of the study.

METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

RESEARCH DESIGN

The present study is conducted to acknowledge the difference in the study habits of boys and girls of Intermediate Level students of government and private schools of Lucknow District. Keeping in view objectives of the study the investigator has chosen *Descriptive Survey method* for the present study.

VARIABLES:-

Dependent variable: - The dependent variable in the present study is

- ❖ STUDY HABITS

Independent variable: - The independent variables in the present study are:-

- ❖ GOVERNMENT SCHOOLS
- ❖ PRIVATE SCHOOLS
- ❖ GENDER OF THE STUDENTS
- ❖ SCIENCE AND ARTS STREAM.

POPULATION:-

In the present study all the students of XI standard of government and private schools of urban areas of Lucknow District only will be the respondent of this problem. These students were related to different colleges.

SAMPLE:-

The sample selected for the present study is comprised of 200 Intermediate level students in which 100 students are boys and 100 students are girls.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE:-

To select the sample in the present study Probability Sampling technique will be used and in Probability Sampling technique, Simple Random Sampling Method will be used.

Simple random sampling is a sampling technique where every item in the population has an even chance and likelihood of being selected in the sample. Here the selection of items completely depends on chance or by probability .

The total sample comprised of school students with age rang 16 to 18 years. From Lucknow District. The whole sample consist of total 200 students with equal number of boys (n=100) and girls (n=100). Both subgroups were made with equal number of students belong to Lucknow district. The sample distribution is depicted as follows.

TOOL USED IN THE RESEARCH:-

The tool used in the present study is ‘Study Habits Inventory’ (P S S H I) constructed by M. N. Palsane and Sadhana Sharma to measure the study habits of the adolescents.

BRIEF DISCRIPTION OF THE TEST

To test the study habit of students study habit inventory constructed and standardized by M.N.Palsane & Sadhana Sharma has been used. This inventory has 45 statements.

TECHNIQUES USED IN THE RESEARCH:-

In order to meet the specified objectives of the study and arrive at the results following statistical techniques were applied to analyze the data:-

- MEAN
- STANDARD DEVIATION
- T-TEST

MAJOR FINDINGS OF THE RESEARCH

The study has led to the following findings:-

- The perusal of table no.1 makes it clear that mean score of girl’s senior secondary school students (66.64) is higher than the mean score of boys of senior secondary school students (63.98) . Therefore, the difference in their mean score has been found statistically significant at the level 0.05.
Therefore, it has been found that there is significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of government schools.
- The perusal of table no.2 makes it clear that mean score of girl’s senior secondary school students (75.2) is higher than the mean score of boys of senior secondary school students (71.0) . Therefore, the difference in their mean score has been found statistically significant at the level 0.05.

Hence, it has been found that there is significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of private schools.

- The perusal of table no.3 makes it clear that mean score of science stream senior secondary school students (70.5) is higher than the mean score of Arts stream senior secondary school students (67.91) .Therefore, the difference in their mean score has been found statistically significant at the level 0.05

Hence, it has been found that there is significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls Arts and Science stream students.

- The perusal of table no.4 makes it clear that mean score of private senior secondary school students (73.1) is higher than the mean score of government senior secondary school students (65.31) . Therefore, the difference in their mean score has been found statistically significant at the level 0.05.

Hence, it has been found that there is significant difference between the study habits of boys and girls of government schools and private schools.

CONCLUSIONS

After going through the results, findings and discussion, following conclusions are drawn. These conclusions may be seen in accordance with sample and tools used by the investigator:-

- ❖ It can be concluded from the results and findings that girl’s students of senior secondary level have better study habits than boys of senior secondary level, of government schools.
- ❖ It can be concluded from the results and findings that girl’s students of senior secondary level have better study habits than boys of senior secondary level, of private schools.

- ❖ It can be concluded from the analysis of data that science stream students have better study habits than arts stream students.
- ❖ It can be concluded from the analysis of data that private school senior secondary students have better study habits than government school students.
- ❖ Girls of senior secondary school students have better habits of using proper physical conditions for study. They have habit of note taking.
- ❖ Girls of senior secondary school have better memory and have better habit of scheduling time for examination while boys of senior secondary school have poor study habits in comparison of girls.
- ❖ On the whole students of senior secondary level good study habits.

EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATION OF THE RESEARCH FINDINGS

In the present days, study habits are an important factor in the student's academic achievement and personal improvement. At the senior secondary stage, it is essential to focus on the individual to judge his/her habitual deeds up to the expected level or not. If good habits are inculcated, nurtured and promoted at the young and impressionable age of a child, it will go long way in removing a number of hurdles on the way to development of good and cultured citizens.

The present study is of immense educational importance to the students, course writers, teachers, and counsellors. It will help the students to change their faulty study-habits. They should devote equal time to all the subjects. The students should be encouraged to use library books and magazines to develop good study habits. Counselling programs should be organized for the students to develop good study habits in them. The students require more guidance and counselling with regard to study habits so that the students may identify their strengths and weakness in the learning strategies and they may become more conscious about better study habits. There is a need to evolve curricular activities in school programme in which students may actively participate. School education should be made need based and practical oriented. This will promote school effectiveness and hence students' learning.

- Academic achievement of the students is associated with their study habits. Hence, proper study habits may be developed among the students for attaining good Academic achievement.
- The results of the study clearly indicate that students need to improve their study and our schools and parents should help them in this area.
- Students should be made aware with the utility and importance of having good study habit.
- Students should be helped to plan the budget of time for studies.
- The place for study should be calm and quite
- The teachers should try to develop good vocabulary among the students by giving precise meaning of the words.
- Students should prepare an outline and arrange the ideas properly by using logical pattern of presentation.
- Guidance programme in study habits should be organized in schools and colleges.
- The teachers must be encouraged to try out new ideas and tend their day-to-day classroom problems in a scientific manner. The Government and the Managements have to provide the necessary academic facilities for the congenial study conditions in Intermediate colleges.
- Government publications should be made available free of cost to all college libraries.
- Learning through such activities as individual reading, holding group discussions, visiting Places, dramatization, etc., should be encouraged.
- Students with poor study habits have to take the suggestions from their friends and teachers for developing good study habits.
- Students should participate in sports/games, yoga and meditation. These activities make them healthy and keep their minds fresh, which will help for good study habits.
- Students should be motivated to have and develop following good study habits:-
 - Studying on regular basis.
 - Prepare a time table for their study tasks.
 - Prepare proper notes with help of various resources.
 - Develop reading ability by reading text books and other reference books.

- Keep their study place organized neat and free from distraction.
- While learning take breaks.
- Using mnemonics to improve memory planning for regular revisions and practice drills

SUGGESTIONS

SUGGESTIONS FOR THE TEACHERS

- Teachers can practice regularly the study habit techniques through classroom for betterment of teaching learning process.
- Teachers can apply the study habit techniques for remedial teaching.
- Teachers can inculcate proper study habits among the students so that students find easy to learn on higher level.
- Teachers at all level can use study habits techniques for the preparation and planning of their lessons.
- Teachers can motivate the students to follow the study habits in technique in their study.
- Classroom interactions can be improved during teaching learning process by using study habit techniques.

SUGGESTIONS FOR THE HEADMASTER

- Headmasters can guide motivate the different subject teachers to practice novel ideas related to study habits in the classroom situation.
- Head masters can guide the teachers and students about the study habit techniques and its effect on achievement.
- To develop good study habits various programmes can be arranged in the school.
- Headmaster can organize orientation programmes in their schools for parents on study habits in the schools.

SUGGESTIONS FOR THE PARENTS

- Parents can attend the orientation programme on the study habits
- Parents can motivate the students to follow study habit technique in their study.
- Parents can guide the students about study habit technique and its effect on the achievement.

SUGGESTIONS FOR THE STUDENTS

- Students can improve their study habits and achieve good marks academically.
- Students will know where they are mistaken while studying so they can improve it.
- Students will know their weakness and improve themselves and also take teachers help in it.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FURTHER RESEARCH

The present study is delimited to certain areas due to limited resources and time. On the basis of findings and experiences of the researcher following suggestions are made for the further research.

- 1) The study is delimited to one district only. It can be applied to other districts and the whole state.
- 2) The study is delimited to class 11th students and only. The study can be done including other classes also.
- 3) The study is limited to only comparing the difference between study habits of boys and girls. A similar kind of study can also be done on factors affecting study habits.
- 4) A study on relationship between study habits and various other factors like Personality, intelligence, maturity, home environment, etc can also be done.
- 5) A study can be done on study habits and achievement and its affect on the personality of the students.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Best, J.W., & Kahn, J.V. (2005). Research in Education. {M. Ed.}. New Delhi: Prentice Hall Publications.
- Christian, J. (1983). Study habits as a function of need achievement. Asian Journal of Psychology & Education, 11(1), 6-12. Retrieved from <http://psvcnet.apa.org/psvcinfo/1984-24466-001>

- Mangal, S.K. (2012). Statistics in Education and Psychology. (2nd Ed.) PHI Learning private Limited. New Delhi- 110001.
- Suneetha, B., & Mayuri, K. (2001). A study on age and gender difference on the factors affecting high academic achievement. Journal of Community Guidance and Research, 18(2), 197-208.